

QISQARTMA KONUSLARINI TOPISH.**Abdullayev Sarvar Anvar o'g'li**

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Annotatsiya Bu ish darajali geometriyaning chiziqli bo'lmagan masalalarga qo'llanilishiga bag'ishlangan. Bu ishda Analitik funksiyalarning lokal masalalaridan biri hisoblangan Nyuton ko'pyoqligi yordamida qisqartmalar konuslarini topish masalasi qaralgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nyuton ko'pyoqi, qisqartma konusi, daraja tashuvchilar, tayanch to'g'ri chiziq.

APPLICATION OF THE MATRIX METHOD IN SEARCHING THE CHARACTERISTICS OF ROBOTIC MECHANISMS

Abstract. The increase in the degree of freedom of mechanisms, in turn, leads to an increase in their special cases. When the mechanisms fall into a special state, the degree of freedom decreases, which can lead to a violation of their performance function. In order to prevent the mechanisms from falling into a special state, it is necessary to fully study their structure. This work is devoted to the study of this problem.

Key words: Planar mechanism, degrees of freedom, singularity, Newton's polynomial, reduced cone

Faraz qilaylik, $\Gamma_j^{(d)}$ - Γ ko'pburchakning qandaydir qirrasi yoki uchi bo'lsin. Barcha shunday P vektorlar to'plamini topish kerakki, ular uchun $\Gamma_j^{(d)} = L_p \cap \Gamma$ bo'lsin, ya'ni L_p tayanch to'g'ri chiziq Γ ko'pburchak bilan faqat $\Gamma_j^{(d)}$ lar bo'yichagina kesishsin.

Bunday P vektorlar to'plamini $\Gamma_j^{(d)}$ uchning yoki qirraning konusi deymiz va $K_j^{(d)}$ bilan belgilaymiz. Shunday qilib,

$$K_j^{(d)} = \{P: L_p \cap \Gamma = \Gamma_j^{(d)}\}$$

$\tilde{Q} \in \Gamma_j^{(d)}$ bo'lsin. $K_j^{(d)}$ konusning P vektorlari quyidagi tengliklar va tengsizliklar sistemalari orqali aniqlanishi ravshan:

$$\text{barcha, } Q \in \Gamma_j^{(d)} \text{ larda } (Q, P) = (\tilde{Q}, P),$$

$$\text{barcha, } Q \in \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_j^{(d)} \text{ larda } (Q, P) < (\tilde{Q}, P).$$

Bu shartlardan birinchisi shuni ko'rsatadiki, $(Q, P) = (\tilde{Q}, P)$ to'g'ri chiziq $\Gamma_j^{(d)}$ to'plamni o'zida saqlaydi: ikkinchi shart bo'lsa, bu to'g'ri chiziq Γ ko'pburchak uchun tayanch to'g'ri chiziq ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Γ ko'pburchak D to'plam nuqtalarining qavariq qobig'i, $\Gamma_j^{(d)}$ bo'lsa $D_j^{(d)}$ to'plamning qavariq qobig'i bo'lganligi sababli, $K_j^{(d)}$ konusni berishda faqatgina D ning nuqtalarini berish yetarli, ya'ni biror $\tilde{Q} \in D_j^{(d)}$ uchun

$$K_j^{(d)} = \left\{ P: \begin{array}{l} (Q, P) = (\tilde{Q}, P) \text{ barcha } Q \in D_j^{(d)} \text{ da,} \\ (Q, P) < (\tilde{Q}, P) \text{ barcha } Q \in D \setminus D_j^{(d)} \end{array} \right\}$$

Misol:

$$f = 2x^4 -$$

$$3x^2y + y^2 + y^4$$

Bunda $Q_1 = (4,0)$, $Q_2 = (2,1)$, $Q_3 = (0,2)$, $Q_4 = (0,4)$ (1-chizma)

Q_1, Q_3, Q_4

nuqtalar uchlardan iborat.

$$\Gamma_1^{(0)} = Q_1, \quad \Gamma_2^{(0)} = Q_3, \quad \Gamma_3^{(0)} = Q_4$$

Belgilashlarni kiritamiz. U holda $\Gamma_1^{(1)}$ - Q_1 va Q_3 uchli qirra, $\Gamma_2^{(1)}$ - Q_3 va Q_4 uchli qirra, $\Gamma_3^{(1)}$ - Q_1 va Q_4 uchli qirra.

$D_j^{(d)}$ to'plamlar quyidagilardan iborat

$$D_1^{(0)} = Q_1, \quad D_2^{(0)} = Q_3, \quad D_3^{(0)} = Q_4$$

$$D_1^{(1)} = Q_1 \cup Q_2 \cup Q_3 \quad D_2^{(1)} = Q_3 \cup Q_4 \quad D_3^{(1)} = Q_4 \cup Q_1$$

Bularga f funksiyaning oltita qisqartmasi mos keladi:

$$\hat{f}_1^{(0)} = 2x^4, \quad \hat{f}_2^{(0)} = y^2, \quad \hat{f}_3^{(0)} = y^4$$

$$\hat{f}_1^{(1)} = 2x^4 - 3x^2y + y^2, \quad \hat{f}_2^{(1)} = y^2 + y^4, \quad \hat{f}_3^{(1)} = 2x^4 + y^4$$

Endi $K_j^{(1)}$ konuslarni topamiz. (ularni biz $f_j^{(d)}$ qisqartmalarning konuslari deb ataymiz) quyidagilarni hosil qilamiz

$$K_2^{(1)} = \{P: (\Gamma_2^{(0)}, P) = (\Gamma_3^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_1^{(0)}, P)\} = \{P: p_2 = 0, p_1 < 0\}$$

$$K_3^{(1)} = \{P: (\Gamma_3^{(0)}, P) = (\Gamma_1^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_2^{(0)}, P)\} = \{P: p_2 = p_1 > 0\}$$

$$K_1^{(0)} = \{P: (\Gamma_1^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_2^{(0)}, P), (\Gamma_1^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_3^{(0)}, P)\} = \{P: p_1 > p_2, p_2 < 2p_1\}$$

$$K_2^{(0)} = \{P: (\Gamma_2^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_1^{(0)}, P), (\Gamma_2^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_3^{(0)}, P)\} = \{P: p_2 > 2p_1, p_2 < 0\}$$

$$K_3^{(0)} = \{P: (\Gamma_3^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_1^{(0)}, P), (\Gamma_3^{(0)}, P) > (\Gamma_2^{(0)}, P)\} = \{P: p_2 > p_1, p_2 > 0\}$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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